

Synthesis of Some N_1 -Substituted-3,5-Dimethyl Pyrazoles and N_1 -Substituted-3-Methyl-5-Pyrazolones and Related Compounds as Potential Fungicides

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Six N_1 -aroyl/aryloxyacetyl-3,5-dimethylpyrazoles, ten N_1 -aroyl/aryloxyacetyl-3-methyl-5-pyrazolones, twenty N_1 -aroyl/aryloxyacetyl-3-methyl-4-arylideno-2-pyrazolone-5-ones and five 1-aryl-1,1-bis- $[N_1$ -aroyl/aryloxyacetyl-3'-methyl-5'-hydroxy pyrazol-4'-yl]-methanes were prepared. Thirty two compounds have been screened against *A. flavus* and *A. niger* and found to possess moderate to fairly good antifungal activity.

SUBSTITUTED pyrazoles have been reported as anticancer¹, antifungal^{1,2}, insecticidal³ and effective antibacterial⁴ agents. Various 1-aryloxyalkyl pyrazoles have been evaluated as hypoglycemic, antiinflammatory and antiviral agents⁵. Many 1,3-disubstituted pyrazol-5-ones and derivatives are known to possess significant fungicidal^{2,6} and antibacterial^{7,8} activities. In view of this we have synthesised the title compounds which are expected to show enhance pesticidal activity due to presence of an aryloxyacetyl/carbonyl moiety.

N_1 -Aroyl/aryloxyacetyl-3,5-dimethyl pyrazoles(I) have been prepared by reaction of acetylacetone and aroyl/aryloxyacetyl hydrazines. N_1 -Aroyl/aryloxyacetyl-3-methyl-5-pyrazolones(II) were prepared by refluxing a mixture of ethylacetoacetate and aroyl/aryloxyacetyl hydrazines. Pyrazolone(II) reacts with an aryl aldehyde in presence of fused sodium acetate and acetic acid to yield corresponding mono-arylidene derivative(III), while similar condensation in presence of piperidine afforded bis-pyrazolyl methane(IV). The compounds (IV) gave violet colouration with ferric chloride and show no $>C=O$ absorption but a broad peak at $\sim 3400\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in IR spectra indicating the presence of enolic hydroxyl group.

The compounds were authenticated by elemental analyses, IR spectra and molecular weight determinations.

The compounds thus prepared are given in Tables 1-4 along their antifungal data. All the compounds gave consistent N, analysis.

SCHEME 1

Experimental

Aroyl/aryloxyacetyl hydrazines :

These were prepared by the method of Conti⁹.

N_1 -Aroyl/aryloxyacetyl -3,5-dimethyl pyrazoles (I)¹⁰ :

A mixture of an ethanolic suspension (20 ml) of aroyl/aryloxyacetyl hydrazine (0.01 M) and acetylacetone (0.01 M) was refluxed gently for two hours.

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TABLE 1—N₁-AROYL/ARYLOXYACETYL-3,5-DIMETHYL PYRAZOLES(I)

No.	R	m.p. °C	Yield %	Fungicidal activity Concn. 10 ppm	
				<i>A. flavus</i>	<i>A. niger</i>
1. ^a	4-Cl.C ₆ H ₄	288	62.1	38.4	36.6
2.	2-HO.C ₆ H ₄	306	33.8	28.3	25.4
3.	1-C ₆ H ₅ .NH.C ₆ H ₄	viscous liquid	53.5	—	—
4.	2-CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄ -O-CH ₃	171	20.4	—	—
5. ^b	4-CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄ -O-CH ₃	242	45.9	48.5	45.0
6.	4-(CH ₃) ₂ .C ₆ H ₃ -O-CH ₃	330	45.4	75.7	74.4

IR spectral data ν_{max} in cm⁻¹

		<i>p</i> -disubstituted benzene	C-Cl		
^a	1600	1490	—	810	730
^b	1700	1600	1240	825	—

TABLE 2—N₁-AROYL/ARYLOXYACETYL-3-METHYL-5-PYRAZOLONES(II)

No.	R	m.p. °C	Yield %	Fungicidal activity Concn. -10 ppm	
				<i>A. flavus</i>	<i>A. niger</i>
7.	4-Cl.C ₆ H ₄	95	89.8	31.6	27.5
8.	2-HO.C ₆ H ₄	146	95.0	24.7	22.4
9.	2-C ₆ H ₅ .NH.C ₆ H ₄	31	78.3	27.3	24.8
10. ^c	C ₆ H ₅ -O-CH ₃	62	93.9	33.4	29.8
11.	2-CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄ -O-CH ₃	94	94.7	36.7	31.2
12.	4-CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄ -O-CH ₃	85	96.4	37.4	33.0
13.	2-Cl.C ₆ H ₄ -O-CH ₃	150	87.2	—	—
14. ^d	4-Cl.C ₆ H ₄ -O-CH ₃	100	97.0	45.8	40.4
15.	4-(CH ₃) ₂ .C ₆ H ₃ -O-CH ₃	101	84.0	69.5	65.2
16.	2-(CH ₃) ₂ CH-5-CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₃ -O-CH ₃	89.90	96.5	64.3	62.7

IR Spectral data ν_{max} in cm⁻¹

		<i>p</i> -disubstituted benzene	C-Cl		
^c	1690	1600	1500	1220	—
^d	1725	1700	1600	1280	755

TABLE 3—N₁-AROYL/ARYLOXYACETYL-3-METHYL-4-ARYLIDENO-2-PYRAZOLINE-5-ONES(III)

No.	R	R'	m.p. °C	Yield %	Fungicidal activity Concn. -10 ppm	
					<i>A. flavus</i>	<i>A. niger</i>
17.	2-HO.C ₆ H ₄	H	170	65.3	36.8	34.0
18. ^e	2-HO.C ₆ H ₄	Cl	186	65.3	42.0	38.5
19.	2-HO.C ₆ H ₄	HO	266	71.4	37.3	34.8
20.	2-HO.C ₆ H ₄	(CH ₃) ₂ N	228	66.2	—	—
21.	C ₆ H ₅ -O-CH ₃	H	146	56.2	43.0	39.8
22.	C ₆ H ₅ -O-CH ₃	Cl	123	56.2	46.8	43.5
23.	C ₆ H ₅ -O-CH ₃	HO	245	44.0	—	—
24.	C ₆ H ₅ -O-CH ₃	(CH ₃) ₂ N	110	65.3	44.2	42.2
25.	2-CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄ -O-CH ₃	H	122	56.3	—	—
26.	2-CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄ -O-CH ₃	Cl	108	67.0	48.2	44.8
27.	2-CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄ -O-CH ₃	HO	165	48.5	39.3	37.6
28.	2-CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄ -O-CH ₃	(CH ₃) ₂ N	168	55.2	43.2	40.5
29. ^f	4-CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄ -O-CH ₃	H	136	54.5	—	—
30.	4-CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄ -O-CH ₃	Cl	116	67.4	50.6	48.8
31.	4-CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄ -O-CH ₃	HO	218 ^d	48.0	42.4	38.6
32.	4-CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄ -O-CH ₃	(CH ₃) ₂ N	115	62.0	—	—
33.	4-Cl.C ₆ H ₄ -O-CH ₃	H	115	54.5	—	—
34. ^g	4-Cl.C ₆ H ₄ -O-CH ₃	Cl	135	48.3	62.3	56.7
35.	4-Cl.C ₆ H ₄ -O-CH ₃	HO	242 ^d	45.6	47.1	43.6
36.	4-Cl.C ₆ H ₄ -O-CH ₃	(CH ₃) ₂ N	120	53.6	56.0	50.4

IR Spectral data ν_{max} in cm⁻¹

		<i>p</i> -disubstituted benzene	C-Cl		
^e	3200	1675	1600	1500	735
^f	3000	1690	1600	1500	—
^g	3050	1700	1600	1520	750

TABLE 4—1-ARYL-1,1-bis-[N₁'-AROYL/ARYLOXYACETYL-3'-METHYL-5'-HYDROXYPYRAZOL-4'-YL]-METHANES(IV)

No.	R	R'	m.p. °C	Yield %	Molecular weight		Fungicidal activity Concn. 10 ppm	
					Found	Calcd.	<i>A. flavus</i>	<i>A. niger</i>
37. ^h	2-HO.C ₆ H ₄	H	68	83.3	539	524	41.3	36.5
38.	4-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	(CH ₃) ₂ N	66	66.2	620.4	604	45.7	39.2
39.	4-CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄ -O-CH ₃	HO	75	67.7	608.7	596	46.8	41.3
40. ⁱ	2-Cl.C ₆ H ₄ -O-CH ₃	(CH ₃) ₂ N	158	77.1	678.2	664	63.6	57.6
41.	2-(CH ₃) ₂ CH-5-CH ₃ . C ₆ H ₄ -O-CH ₃	Cl	108	57.4	718.5	698	68.5	64.2
	MEMCGE BLITOX 50 WP (Commercial fungicides)						75.4	87.4
							85.5	80.7

IR Spectral data ν_{max} in cm^{-1}

	-OH stretching	-CON	-C=N-	=C-O-C-	o-disubstituted benzene
h	3360	1600	1570	—	730
i	3400	1650	1585	1250	735

To this acetic acid (5 ml) was added and the mixture refluxed further for one hour. A clear solution resulted. On evaporation a solid was obtained which was washed and recrystallised with aqueous ethanol.

*N*₁-Aroyl / aryloxyacetyl - 3 - methyl - 5 - pyrazolones (II)¹¹ :

A mixture of an ethanolic suspension (20 ml) of aroyl/aryloxyacetyl hydrazine (0.01 M) and ethyl-acetoacetate (0.01 M) was refluxed gently for three hours. A clear solution resulted. On evaporation a solid was obtained which was washed and recrystallised with aqueous ethanol.

*N*₁-Aroyl / aryloxyacetyl - 3 - methyl - 4 - arylideno - 2 - pyrazoline-5-ones(III) :

An aroyl/aryloxyacetyl-3-methyl-5-pyrazolone (0.01 M) was dissolved in a minimum of glacial acetic acid. To this fused sodium acetate (2.0 g) and an aryl aldehyde (0.01 M) were added and the mixture refluxed for six hours. It was cooled and poured into cold water. The solid separating out was filtered, washed and recrystallised from aqueous ethanol.

The monoarylidene compounds (III) decolourise bromine water and their formation is further supported by the molecular weight, IR spectra and the elemental analysis results.

1-Aryl-1, 1-bis-[*N*₁'-aroyl/aryloxyacetyl-3'-methyl-5'-hydroxy pyrazol-4'-yl]-methanes (IV) :

A methanolic solution of aroyl/aryloxyacetyl-3-methyl-5-pyrazolone (0.01 M) and aryl aldehyde (0.005 M) was treated with few drops of piperidine and kept at room temperature for several hours till

a crystalline solid separated out. It was filtered off, washed and recrystallised from ethanol.

The bis-pyrazolyl methanes(IV) gave violet colour with ferric chloride solution. Their formation is further supported by the absence of >C=O absorption but presence of a broad peak at $\sim 3400\text{ cm}^{-1}$, characteristic of enolic hydroxyl group in the IR spectra. The molecular weights of compounds (IV) were also in agreement with bis structure.

Fungicidal Screening :

The compounds were screened for their anti-fungal activity against *A. flavus* and *A. niger* by agar plate technique^{12,18} at three different concentrations viz. 1000 ppm, 100 ppm and 10 ppm. Two commercial fungicides MEMCGE and BLITOX 50 WP have also been tested under similar conditions to compare the result. The number of replications in each case was three. The percentage inhibition of growth of fungus colony is given by expression :

$$\text{Percentage inhibition} = \frac{C - T \times 100}{C}$$

where C = diameter of fungus colony (in mm) in control after 96 hours,

T = diameter of fungus colony (in mm) in presence of test chemical after 96 hours.

Results and Discussion

Most of the compounds screened possess moderate to fairly good level of fungicidal activity against both the fungi. The pyrazole(I) No. 6[R = 4-(CH₃)₂C.C₆H₄-O-CH₂-], pyrazolones(II Nos. 15 and 16[R = 4-(CH₃)₂C.C₆H₄-O-CH₂-

2-(CH₃)₂CH-5-CH₃.C₆H₅-O-CH₂-], mono-arylideno pyrazolone(III) No. 34[R=4-Cl.C₆H₄-O-CH₂-, R'=Cl] and bis-pyrazolyl methanes(IV) Nos. 40 and 41 [R=2-Cl.C₆H₄-O-CH₂-, R'=(CH₃)₂N; R=2-(CH₃)₂CH-5-CH₃.C₆H₅-O-CH₂-, R'=Cl] inhibit >60% mycelial growth of both the fungal species even at 10 ppm concentration and display antifungal activity of the order of MEMCGE and BLITOX 50 WP at 1000 and 100 ppm concentrations. In general, pyrazoles(I) are slightly better fungicide than the corresponding pyrazolones(II). Further, bis-pyrazolyl methanes(IV) are more active than the corresponding mono-arylideno pyrazolones(III), which are relatively more potent than the corresponding pyrazolones(II). Introduction of an aryloxyacetyl group at N₁ position invariably increases the antifungal activity of the compound.

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References

1. S. G. FARID SOLIMAN and R. M. SHAFIK, *Pharmazie*, 1975, **30**, 436; *Chem. Abs.*, 1975, **83**, 193164b.
2. S. P. SUMAN and S. C. BAHEL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1979, **56**, 374.
3. H. HOFFMANN and I. HAMMANN, *Ger. Offen.*, 2,420,360 (1975); *Chem. Abs.*, 1976, **84**, 44043e.
4. H. C. MUTREJA, G. S. SHAHARIA and H. R. SHARMA, *Indian J. Chem. Sect. B*, 1978, **16B**, 519.
5. M. WOLF and J. F. DONALD, *U. S.*, 3,190,888 (1965); *Chem. Abs.*, 1965, **63**, 9951f.
6. SUNDER RAO and A. S. MITTRA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1977, **15B**, 1062.
7. U. WRZECIONO, B. KRZYSZTOFIK and E. DANIDEWICZ, *Acta Pol. Pharm.*, 1975, **30**, 433; *Chem. Abs.*, 1976, **84**, 30956t.
8. P. N. DHAL, T. E. ACHARY and A. NAYAK, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1975, **52**, 1196.
9. L. CONTI, *Chem. Abs.*, 1964, **61**, 4253e.
10. H. G. GARG and P. P. SINGH, *J. Chem. Soc., C*, 1969, 1141.
11. A. I. VOGEL, 'A Text Book of Practical Organic Chemistry', Ed. III, 1971, p. 998.
12. J. G. HORSFALL, *Bot. Rev.*, 1945, **11**, 357.
13. U. S. D. A. Circular No. 198 (1931).